

ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BO`LGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. REKURSIV TRAPETSIYALAR QOIDASI.

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Yangi O`zbekistonimizda yuz berayotgan siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ilmiy – texnikaviy va madaniy o`zgarishlar Oliy ta`lim tizimida ham o`z aksini topmoqda. O`zbekistonda uzluksiz ta`lim – tarbiya tizimini yaratish, shu asosida ta`lim sifatini jahon andozalari darajasiga yetkazish ta`lim sistemasining eng dolzarb vazifasiga aylandi.

Hisoblash matematikasi sohasida nazariy izlanishlar asosan, tipik matematik masalalarni yechishning sonli metodlar atrofida guruhlanadi. Bu sohaning klassik masalalaridan biri bu integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash formulalarini qurishdan iborat.

Bir karrali integrallarni son qiymatlari geometrik nuqtai nazardan qisqacha kvadratura deb ataladi.

Bunday masalalar bilan ko`pincha buyuk olimlar shug`ullanganlar. Masalan: Gauss, Chebishev, Eyler, Nyuton va boshqalar.

Kvadratur formular deganda quyidagi taqribiy tenglikni tushunamiz:

$$\int_B f(x)dx \approx \sum_{\lambda=1}^N C_{\lambda} f(x^{(\lambda)}), \quad (a)$$

bu yerda C_{λ} – kvadratur formulaning koeffitsientlari, $x^{(\lambda)}$ – tugun nuqtalari, N – tugun nuqtalar soni[2].

Faraz qilaylik $f(x)$ uzluksiz funksiyani $[a, b]$ kesmada aniq integralni taqribiy hisoblovchi formulani qurish talab qilinsin.

Integralning eng sodda taqribiy ifodasi asosan $[a, b]$ kesma balandligi $f(x)$ ning $\frac{a+b}{2}$ nuqtadagi $f(\frac{a+b}{2})$ qiymatiga teng bo`lgan to`g`ri turtburchak yuzasining kattaligidan iborat.

Quyidagi kvadratur formulani hosil qilamiz.

$$\int_a^b f(x)dx \approx (b-a)f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right), \quad (b)$$

Katta nazariy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan kvadratur formulalar bilan bog'liq hisoblash algoritmlarini optimizizastiyalash masalalari bilan ko'pgina olimlar shug'ullanib kelgan[3-4]. Bulardan S.L.Sobolev, A.N.Kolmogorov, S.M.Nikolskiy va boshqalar.

Kvadratur formulani $p(x)$ - vazn funksiyasi bilan qaraydigan bo'lsak

$$\int_a^b p(x)f(x)dx \approx \sum_{\lambda=1}^N C_{\lambda}f(x^{(\lambda)}), \quad (c)$$

ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

Bu holda xatolik funksionali quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

$$\ell(x) = p(x)\varepsilon_{[a,b]}(x) - \sum_{\lambda=1}^N C_{\lambda}\delta(x - x^{(\lambda)}), \quad (d)$$

Integrallarni taqribiy hisoblash uchun formula qurish hisoblash matematikasi va sonlar nazariyasining bir sinf masalasini tashkil qiladi. Bunday masalalarni yechish bilan juda ko'p taniqli matematiklar shug'ullanishgan, shuning uchun ham juda ko'p formulalar ularning nomlari bilan ataladi, masalan Nyuton, Eyler, Gauss, Chebishev, Markov formulalarini misol keltirish mumkin. Integrallarni taqribiy hisoblashda integral ostidagi funksiya bir o'zgaruvchili bo'lsa unda kvadratur formula deyiladi, bunday masalalar bilan birinchi bo'lib Sard, Nikolskiylar shug'ullangan, agar integral ostidagi funksiya ikki va undan ortiq o'zgaruvchili bo'lsa unda kubatur formula deyiladi, bunday masalalar bilan birinchi bo'lib Sobolev shug'ullangan. **ALGEBRAIK ANIQLIGI YUQORI BO'LGAN KVADRATUR FORMULALAR. REKURSIV TRAPETSIYALAR QOIDASI.**

2^{k-1} panellari yordamida umumlashgan trapetsiya qoidasi bilan hisoblangan I_k integral berilgan bo'lsin. Agar k bittaga ortadigan bo'lsa, panellar soni ikki barobar ortadi.

$$H = b - a \quad (1)$$

belgilanishdan foydalanib

$$I = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} I_i = [f(x_0) + 2f(x_1) + 2f(x_2) + 2f(x_3) + \dots + 2f(x_{n-1}) + 2f(x_n)] \frac{h}{2}$$

tenglamada $k=1; 2$ va 3 uchun quyidagi natijalarni topamiz.

$k = 1$ (bitta panel):

$$I_1 = [f(a) + f(b)] \frac{H}{2} \quad (2)$$

$k = 2$ (ikkita panellar):

$$I_2 = \left[f(a) + 2f\left(a + \frac{H}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] \frac{H}{4} = \frac{1}{2} I_1 + f\left(a + \frac{H}{2}\right) \frac{H}{2} \quad (3)$$

$k = 3$ (uchta panellar):

$$\begin{aligned} I_3 &= \left[f(a) + 2f\left(a + \frac{H}{4}\right) + 2f\left(a + \frac{H}{2}\right) + 2f\left(a + \frac{3H}{4}\right) + f(b) \right] \frac{H}{8} = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} I_2 + \left[f\left(a + \frac{H}{4}\right) + f\left(a + \frac{3H}{4}\right) \right] \frac{H}{4} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Endi biz ixtiyoriy $k > 1$ son uchun quyidagiga ega bo`lamiz:

$$I_k = \frac{1}{2} I_{k-1} + \frac{H}{2^{k-1}} \sum_{i=1}^{2^{k-2}} f\left[a + \frac{(2i-1)H}{2^{k-1}} \right], \quad k = 2, 3, \dots \quad (5 a)$$

bu rekursiv trapetsiya qoidasidir. Yig`indida panellar sonini ikki baravar ortirganimizda yangi tugun nuqtalar hosil bo`ladi. Demak (2) va (5) tenglamalardan $I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_k$ ketma - ketligini hisoblashda to`g`ridan - to`g`ri tenglamadan I_k ni hisoblaymiz. Rekursiv trapetsiya qoidasidan foydalanishning afzalligi shundaki, u konvergentsiyani kuzatish va I_{k-1} va I_k o`rtasidagi farq yetarlicha kichik bo`lganda jarayonni tugatish imkonini beradi. (5 a) tenglamaning eslab qolish osonroq bo`lgan shakli

$$I(h) = \frac{1}{2} I(2h) + h \sum f(x_{new}) \quad (5 b)$$

bo`lib, bu yerda $h = H/n$ har bir panelni yaratadi.

▪ **Trapetsiya usulida integralni hisoblaymiz**

Trapetsiya funksiyasi (2) va (5) tenglamalar yordamida I_{k-1} (Iold) berilgan I_k (Inew) ni hisoblaydi. Istalgan aniqlikka erishilgunga qadar trapesiyani $k = 1, 2, \dots$

bilan chaqirib, $\int_a^b f(x) dx$ ni hisoblashimiz mumkin.

Trapetsiya moduli

modul trapezoid

``` Inew = trapesiya ( f,a,b, Iold,k ).

Rekursiv trapetsiya qoidasi:

eski =  $f(x)$  ning  $x = a$  dan  $b$  gacha bo`lgan integrali bilan hisoblangan

$2^{(k-1)}$  panelli trapetsiya qoidasi.

Inew =  $2^k$  panellar bilan hisoblangan bir xil integral.

```

def trapezoid(f,a,b,Iold ,k):

if k == 1:Inew = (f(a) + f(b))*(b - a)/2.0

else:

n = $2^{(k-2)}$ # Yangi nuqtalar soni

h = (b - a)/n # Yangi nuqtalar oralig`i

x = a + h/2.0

sum = 0.0

for i in range(n):

sum = sum + f(x)

x=x+h

Inew = (Iold + h*sum)/2.0

return Inew

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